

Integration of Education, Business and Marketing Management in Private School Management

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Abstract

Higher education plays a crucial role in the growth and development of any country, wherever it is in the world. It not only trains qualified human resources, but also raises awareness about social issues, political issues, and cultural issues. Citizens with an elevated level of education make significant contributions to raising the general productivity of the society and improving the quality

of life. Many countries around the world distribute great resources to the creation of new education programs and the improvement of existing programs to reach the social and economic development levels they have determined for themselves. This situation has caused the private sector to be more involved in the provision of higher education. These companies, which provide services for special education, enter the market with the dual aims of maximizing their profits and fulfilling their respective social duties. Because the needs of students and the demands of the market are different, many courses related to both domestic and international institutions are included in the curriculum of private colleges. This has resulted in an increased level of competition among private institutions to recruit more students. As a result, they use a wide variety of marketing methods to advertise their establishments. According to the results of the study, both long-term and short-term plans are used, and a marketing strategy is applied to direct the operations of the institutions. Bamfa (2013) conducted a study to decide the impact of marketing messages on the number of students enrolled in private colleges in Ghana. It has been discovered that private education institutions have better opportunities to position themselves better and, as a result, to gain a lasting competitive advantage in the sector, if they run their advertising campaigns effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: *Education in Private School Management, Business in Private Schools, Marketing Management in Private Schools, Integration in Private School Management*

1. Introduction

Odio (2014) on the variables that affect students' enrollment in social studies education, career opportunities, gender, and environmental factors, they play a role in students' decision to enroll in social studies education. Fosu (2014) tried to find the crucial factors that play a role in the decision-making process of students about university selection. According to the findings of the study, the most crucial factors affecting students' decisions about which university they will go to are the availability of course options, the quality of the instructors, the quality of the library and internet resources, and the adaptability of the curriculum. When Yamamoto (2006) examined the university

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selection criteria of students to improve university management using marketing tools, he discovered that families are a crucial factor in the decision-making process in university selection.

Kotler (two thousand), a positive image is an especially important asset in the market. As a result, prospective students are more interested in enrolling in private vocational college. For private institutions to be successful, therefore, they must work hard to deliver high-quality goods and services and to garner as much positive attention as possible. Only then can they hope to achieve the desired results. Marketing activities are not only economic activities undertaken by educational institutions to attract students; rather, marketing activities are an effort to improve the quality of education as a kind of duty to the wider community. Educational institutions need to constantly renew their strategies to ensure that they are in line with the demands of their external environment and that they can compete with the strengths within their own institutions. The ability to manage and strategize the marketing of one's products is necessary for education service providers such as higher education institutions to meet consumer demand.

It is since the producers cannot market their goods, that the quality of that product is not appreciated by the society, that it does not supply any added value to the personal development of the individual and that it cannot supply a satisfactory service. The effect of this does not exclude the possibility that it was one of the causes of the collapse of a university, which means that it will eventually result in possibly imposing a closure on the college. If the college is closed due to the incompetence of the administrators, it will cause some problems in a society. It should come as no surprise that private institutions can adapt to an ever-changing environment to keep up with the increasing levels of intense and complex competition and the amount of momentum that is occurring .

Students and individuals interested in enrolling in an educational institution should be attracted above all because it offers the best possible services. In addition to the ardent desire from the leaders of educational institutions to make educational institutions that can provide excellent service (applied value-oriented), setting up a close relationship with the customer is essential to achieve customer satisfaction. For an educational institution to supply excellent service to students, it must be done optimally and completely (by knitting by hand), not reluctantly, so that the students

as the serviced party are satisfied. A conversation about the increase in the total number of new students enrolled in higher education can in no way be separated from a discussion about the overall excellence of the institution.

2. Marketing of Educational Services

Quality management is essential since quality is a constantly changing situation that depends on the products, services, people, processes and atmosphere of educational institutions and higher education programs that have achieved their goals. Specifically, the customers in question are students. Therefore, the marketing of educational services is an activity that educational institutions do when supplying services or delivering educational services to customers in a correct and satisfactory manner. For this reason, business and marketing educate the public and guide them to the right path so that they believe and convince the public that the higher education service products offered by the public are the products of quality educational institutions in terms of education and training, not with advertisements and promotions that mislead the public. This is done so that people believe and believe that the higher education service products offered are the products of quality educational institutions in terms of inputs, processes, and results. The community or stakeholders will experience a sense of satisfaction because of the quality of the educational service products provided. In the end, everything education services marketers do comes down to the value that education services customers provide in exchange for the happiness they experience. The creation of satisfied customers (consumers) can result in several positive outcomes, including setting up a harmonious relationship between the company and the customer, setting up a good foundation for repeat business and building customer loyalty and loyalty.

Tjiptono (1996) writes, "Customer satisfaction is the core capital for companies in building customer loyalty."

When customers are satisfied with a product or service, they are more likely to buy that product or service and are also more likely to recommend it to their friends. In addition, producers will make many profits because of useful information spread by consumers from customers to other

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consumers. The most important aspects of marketing can be divided into three categories as follows:

- (a) *Market segmentation and organizing them into diverse groups, commonly known as the process of separating individual customers or consumers. Each of these customers has a unique set of characteristics, product requirements and preferences in terms of their marketing mix.*
- (b) *Targeting, which refers to the process of selecting one or more market sectors for participation.*
- (c) *Positioning, also known as analysis of a company's place in the market. Customers' minds need to be shaped around the competitive advantages already available for products in the market and these benefits need to be communicated to them.*

The main purpose of marketing (marketing) in the field of education is to improve the feeling of the public towards educational institutions. The aim is to encourage people in the local community to take advantage of the educational opportunities these educational institutions offer. There are many different methods of creating this picture, and it all depends on the member of the society you are trying to portray. If most of our target audience is potential consumers with limited means, we will need to develop the impression that our madrasas are more affordable than they are. If middle and upper economic groups are the target consumers and are willing to pay more for better quality of service, the image we need to create is that our private universities serve better than other foundation universities, even if they must pay a price.

Therefore, education marketing is important as a step in balancing the position of education in the age of global competitiveness. The marketing function of education and school services is part of a marketing technique that aims to achieve better results compared to marketing techniques that do not reach the targeted number of students or users of educational services as desired. The goal of this technique is to achieve overall better results (Mantja , 2002). Also, examples of ideas implemented by an organization or educational institution area. The Idea Behind Production According to this theory, people should choose what suits their needs and abilities.

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Supplying the highest possible level of service to students and their families is at the heart of the marketing strategies used by educational institutions. It is one of the five most crucial factors or determinants that decide the quality of education services that teachers and instructors can supply services as promised, in a reliable, correct and consistent manner.

- a. *Reliability (authenticity) is another term for this aspect of service delivery.*
- b. *Talent, also known as responsiveness, refers to the willingness of employees and agents to aid customers and deliver services in a prompt and meaningful way.*

In addition, responsiveness refers to the willingness to listen to and resolve complaints raised by consumers or users of educational services, such as supplying proper tools to ensure that the correct procedure is followed.

- c. *Assurance that refers to the ability of employees to instill confidence and belief in customers in the commitments made to them, such as those made in the context of sales campaigns.*
- d. *Empathy refers to the willingness of teachers or lecturers or staff and administrators to be more concerned about giving personal attention, among other people, to teachers or lecturers and employees who need to position themselves as students or parents and customers. empathetic teachers or lecturers or staff and administrators would be ideal.*

After receiving a complaint from a customer, it is important to show genuine concern for the person's well-being to find a satisfactory solution. Concrete (Fungible) , also known as the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, and other communication materials .

This includes things like regular spatial organization as well as buildings and the cleanliness of buildings. Given the increase in the number of new students enrolling in the school, the quality of the education supplied will not compromise in any way. Because quality is a constantly changing situation, whether they achieve the goal is linked to things like goods, services, people, procedures and even the atmosphere of the school. Education is considered as the most valuable investment in terms of increasing the level of human resources of a country to ease the national development process. This value is decided by the percentage of the educated population. The higher the

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education level in a community, the further the country will go in development (Qomar , 2007). One of the key factors for the success of educational qualification in today's highly competitive education environment is how satisfied customers are with the educational services they receive. It is understood that supplying education is not the only way education can contribute to national development; The contribution of education to national development is quality education measured in terms of its inputs, processes, outputs and results (Qomar , 2015).

When the educational process is of high quality, it will result in a sense of satisfaction among community members and student parents. In the end, everything education services marketers do comes down to the value that education services customers provide in exchange for the happiness they experience.

Recognizing the importance of competitor activities and monitoring developments in competing schools can have a positive impact on decision making, particularly through the development of new initiatives such as added services for both students and parents.

3. Cross-Functional Coordination

The fundamental belief that developing superior value for target customers is crucial to a school's success in a competitive market is a belief that should be shared by all members of the school. This is necessary so that the core belief is shared by all members of the school. But this is something that can only be achieved by combining and coordinating the various resources the school has. Everyone in the school community handles bringing in new students and keeping relationships with existing students. This is not just something that should fall under the authority of the school administration. To achieve this goal, the staff in the school, the market environment, the community, etc. have full access to competitive information, including The third part includes the coordinated and integrated application of corporate resources to synthesize and give market intelligence to engage processes to build and keep strong relationships with customers. This is done to meet the requirements of the third element, called "market intelligence". There is some

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empirical evidence from commercial and service sector organizations to suggest that market orientation has a positive impact on organisations.

A market-oriented school culture places a higher priority on supplying excellent customer service (process-oriented) rather than focusing solely on student academic success (result-oriented). A market-oriented school has a set of beliefs and values held in common. These; organizational pride, customer service, service quality, innovation, open-mindedness, sense of purpose, entrepreneurship, superior performance in competition and targeting excellence. Schools that share the principles of clear internal communication are more likely to be market oriented. This is because market information is not kept by the school administration but is instead gave to the school.

Also, the degree of competition intensity is likely to decide the rate at which a firm moves to market. This means that school's function in an atmosphere that is both predictable and coherent (Carlson, 1965). In other words, educators around the world show an elevated level of resistance to embracing competitive values (Oplatka , 2006; Oplatka et al. 2002). As a result, it is extremely difficult to undermine the value system under which they currently run. For example, during many interviews, teachers categorically said that "education is incompatible with marketing", "teachers are paid only to teach, not to market their schools", or "professional teachers know what children need". These claims have been made many times (Oplatka , Hemsley -Brown and Foskett , 2002). Using the “shock” method is something Bat (1994) recommends using when cultural scenarios are deeply held by school members and their power is difficult to weaken . The use of shock techniques may seem immoral and inappropriate for training to some educators; however, this approach stems from the assumption that it may take an indefinite period to wait for individuals to undertake cultural change of their own accord.

Most people, even trainers, prefer things to stay the same, even if it is more expensive for them overall. Even in schools that have experienced a significant drop in enrollment, our own research shows that many teachers have for many years adhered to traditional values proper to the coherent, non-competitive environment of schools (for example, there is no need for marketing).

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Expanding rather than narrowing the practical options open to them and negotiating among themselves the potential values and norms suitable for transforming the school culture into a market-oriented culture are the goals of this phase. The purpose of this phase is not to help school staff come to terms with the proposed cultural change; rather, it is to allow them to take part in the creation of these terms. The principal, as well as any school administrator who conducts such "negotiation", must be equipped with the necessary skills to take on the various tasks that await them. These include:

“to develop an atmosphere conducive to discussion and debate on the development of market orientation; consider alternative and opposition positions for competitive perspective; and coordinating the participation of different individuals from various departments”

These randomly held meetings should include a general discussion about the results of competition and customer satisfaction levels for the education system, as well as a discussion about the needs of society soon.

For the purposes of this research, large schools are considered to have a total enrollment of more than three hundred students. Due to the reputation and limited enrollment opportunities of larger schools, smaller schools have no choice but to create their own unique identity to compete with larger schools. This can be conducted by marketing students' distinctive qualities to prospective students and their parents. Due to market pressures, it has become difficult for small schools to keep or increase enrollment. Although overall gains are a net loss of registrations of 3% compared to registrations that existed before 2007, it is possible to assume that the increase was a result of the booming economy. Conceptual Supports Attitude theories and Fishbein's Multi-Attribute Model are the main sources of inspiration for this research (1977). These ideas are based on the premise that consumers' attitudes can be changed by presenting the attributes of a product to the customer in a way that increases the value of the product. According to Fishbein's hypothesis, one's attitude influences their intentions, which in turn leads to their actions and behaviors. The level of influence of a trait on an attitude can be judged by the actions it elicits. Collecting data on the school administrator's perceived view of the effectiveness of certain marketing strategies aimed at creating value for students' prospective parents allows behavior to be predicted. These strategies

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aim to create value for prospective parents of students. It is possible to find consumers' attitudes as well as their intentions, which should lead to some form of action being taken.

The theory states that in the scenario of parents considering enrolling their children in an independent school, the parent already has an idea about the thirteen schools and an effective marketing strategy proves the characteristics of the independent school. Characteristics produce or endorse an attitude that ultimately leads to a behavior. Information that influences customer attitude and supplies decision-making context is filtered and informed by effective marketing. According to research (Laga and Eggert , 2006; Moliner , Sánchez , Rodriguez , and Callarisa , 2007), Relationship Marketing (RM) and Transactional Marketing (TM) theories influence attitudes and methods that influence registration. The ego, social acceptability, and ideals can all play a role in the formation of consumer attitudes. One-on-one interviews and surveys on the perceived success of marketing tactics using TM or RM are two methods that can be used to discover which marketing approaches have the most impact on enrollment. According to Moliner , Sánchez , Rodriguez , and Callarisa (2007), value is created by the marketing strategy that most effectively conveys the characteristics of the school, and as a result, it is the desired action to register. Thus, the dependent variable would be the process of a child's enrollment in a particular school.

Modern parents have extremely lofty standards for the educational institutions where their children attend, and educational institutions are in constant competition with each other to recruit new students (Oplatka2007:218). Prospective parents in South Africa do not have to enroll their children in the school geographically closest to their home; instead, they are given the choice to enroll their children in the school of their choice (Van Wyk & Bisschoff 2012:431). Public schools and independent schools are the two main types of schools recognized to exist in the country by the South African Schools Act (No. 84 of 1996). After the law was passed in 1996, all schools previously classified as public or state-sponsored were reclassified as public schools, and all schools previously classified as private were folded into the category of independent schools (Governing Bodies Federation). South African Schools 2013). The number of independent schools in South Africa has more than tripled since 1994, when there were only 518 of them. There were 1571 independent schools in 2012 (Roodt 2011:2). It is possible that parents lose their trust in the

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public education system, as this increase in the number of students attending private schools is a sign (International Finance Corporation 2010). The expanding middle class seeking a higher quality education in South Africa and the failure of the government to build new schools in wealthier areas are major factors driving the rise of private school management (Hasenfuss 2011). In general, parents are more selective when choosing a school for their children and they do their own work before enrolling their children in a particular institution (Molland 2007:22). Consumers are actively involved in the decision-making process and have advanced knowledge about the options available to them (Petruzzellis & Romanazzi 2010:149). In the South African context, education is seen as a service, and in 2009 the service sector accounted for 70 percent of the country's gross domestic product (Boshoff & Du Plessis 2009:4). However, education is an intangible service (Can't & Van Heerden 2010:450), which makes it difficult for parents to choose a suitable educational environment for their children. The pre-purchase stage, the service encounter stage, and the post encounter stage constitute the three stages that make up the decision-making process for services (Wells and Foxall 2012: 128). In this article, we will focus on the third and last step of the pre-purchase phase, which is the examination of different options.

Evaluation criteria are the criteria that consumers find acceptable when seeking solutions to their problems. In addition, evaluation criteria are aspects or characteristics that consumers look for when buying a particular product or service (Hawkins, Mothersbough & Mookerjee 2010:649). According to Losike-Sedimo (2011:39), it is crucial for schools, parents, and prospective parents to understand how to supply the highest level of service to their customers by learning what their children (parents) want for their educational experience. There is an extremely limited amount of research specifically on school marketing in South Africa. This includes research conducted by McAlister (2005:2), in which the researcher tries to decide the importance of marketing in the market for independent schools in South Africa and to understand the management's perspective on marketing. Malherbe (2004:82) conducted a study to decide whether independent schools in Gauteng adopt a marketing culture and to analyze the effect of such marketing on the image of independent schools. In the case of independent primary schools, little has been done in South Africa on the factors that influence parents' school choice decisions.

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The wording of the problem is that some independent schools find it difficult to market themselves effectively due to a lack of knowledge of the selection factors parents set when choosing an independent school. This lack of information makes it difficult for parents to choose an independent school (BJ Fourie pers. comm., January 12, 2012). As for choosing an independent primary school for their children in Gauteng, the main aim of the researcher in this study was to decide the considerations of prospective parents. Supplying marketing advice to independent schools to aid such institutions in their efforts to increase enrollment will aid the above-mentioned schools. A literature analysis on the marketing of independent schools, the consumer decision-making process, the selection factors of parents who choose independent schools, and a description of the issue investigated is included in this article.

One of the key issues of discussion focused on the question of whether educational institutions should revise their dogmas to reflect a more socially conscious stance that strikes a healthy balance between human well-being and profit maximization (Garca. Feijoo et al., 2020; Laszlo et al., 2017; Rocha . et al., 2020). One of the consequences of this dialogue has been the need for business schools to restructure not only their approach to teaching and research (Sadler -Smith & Cojuharenco , 2021), but also the value proposition they provide to their large customers, who are businesses (David et al., 2011). There is evidence that business schools are responding to this demand (Garcia- Feijoo et al., 2020; Laszlo et al., 2017). It can be exemplified by the gradual reorganization of business school outputs from one that primarily reflects subject "hard skills" (such as applying theory to management, marketing, and finance) to something that includes "soft skills" (such as communicating about management). Marketing or finance matters, with components outside the major or department becoming increasingly relevant in both business and social contexts) is a result of this gradual reorganization (Trkman , 2019).

4. Where Knowledge, Skills and Talents Coincide with the Characteristics Companies Look for in Candidates in the Recruitment Process

Considering this focus, business educators and managers constantly ask themselves, "Are we adequately educating our students in the responsibilities they will play in the workforce?" they

should question. In other words, can we say that the knowledge, skills and abilities that students graduate from business school match with the characteristics that companies look for in candidates during the recruitment process? According to the findings of academic studies, business schools have made an honest attempt to teach undergraduate students courses that will prepare them for jobs in business (Hamilton et al., 2000). Therefore, it should come as no surprise that almost all business educators have a good self-assessment of the work, they do to prepare these students to succeed in the business world (e.g., Gallup , 2017a; Gallup , 2017b). However, the findings of other studies (for example, Herrington & Arnold, 2013) imply that the effects of such efforts may not be as positive as hoped, as only 11% of employers believe that educational institutions train students adequately for the workforce (Wyman et al., 2018). The extent to which undergraduate business schools teach the skills necessary for cross-functional integration has received a lot of attention recently.

In addition, as CFI consists of three dimensions (collaboration, communication, and communication), the development of a tool to measure CFI will highlight gaps at these levels, thus allowing for more detailed strategies to be developed to reduce the skills gap. This is because CFI consists of collaboration, communication and communication. Overall, the measure can be useful to aid undergraduate business program designers and managers, hiring managers, and researchers in assessing the CFI skills gap and discovering strategies to address it.

There is a discrepancy between the degree of interfunctional collaboration skills that managers in businesses believe their employees have and the level of interfunctional collaboration skills that second half of an undergraduate business school students believe. they have students.

5. Coordination Across Functional Boundaries

According to research conducted by Garner et al. (2019), employee talents related to coordination are a valuable resource for integration. In addition, both human and time management, which is a part of coordination, has been among the most sought-after skills by employers (Petrone , 2019; Volini et al., 2019). wiley Education Services and Future In a survey conducted by Workplace ,

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employers found project management as one of the top five skills employees need. Project management involves a significant amount of coordination (2019). While there is some evidence that work programs ease team-based learning (Haidet et al., 2014), the study does not show that students buy the necessary skills for cross-functional collaboration. On the other hand, autonomy by itself does not always result in improvements unless well supported. It is also essential that school leaders be clearly defined and delimited to ensure that their core duties are conducted effectively. It is important that people in charge of schools first define their role by learning about the strategies most likely to promote education.

Redefine school leadership roles to improve student learning. It is the responsibility of policy makers and practitioners alike to ensure that the roles and responsibilities associated with better learning outcomes are at the center of school leadership practice . According to the findings of this research, there are four key areas of responsibility that school leadership should focus on to improve outcomes for students:

To support, evaluate and improve the quality of teachers, school leaders need to be able to tailor the curriculum to the needs of the local community, encourage teamwork among teachers, and take part in teachers' monitoring, evaluation and professional development.

Policy makers need to ensure that school leaders have discretion in setting strategic direction and perfect their ability to develop school plans and goals and check progress using data to improve implementation. In addition, policy makers need to ensure that school leaders can set academic standards for students. Strategic management of financial and human resources The ability of school leadership teams to effectively manage their financial resources can be enhanced by policy makers by supplying training to school leaders, setting up a role for a financial manager within the leadership team, or supplying training. In addition, school administrators must have the ability to influence choices about teacher recruitment to increase candidates' compliance with the requirements of their own school. Working with other educational institutions is a new direction of leadership that should be recognized as a separate part of school administrators' responsibilities. It can be beneficial not only to students at a single school, but also to students at the entire school system. But school leaders need to develop the skills necessary to be involved in issues that

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transcend the boundaries of their school. Establish leadership frameworks for schools to improve education policy and practice School leadership frameworks can help suggest direction on the key qualities, duties, and obligations of successful school leaders and highlight the important nature of school leadership as follows.

They have the potential to serve as a basis for the systematic recruitment, training, and evaluation of school leaders. Key mandates falling within the remit of school leaders should be detailed within the frameworks and provisions should be made to contextualize regional and institutional standards. They must be produced with the participation of the professional community. Looking at the recent situation, a person who spends limited resources from the education budget loses the chance to meet some of his other demands at the same time. Similarly, spending public money on education means losing the opportunity to invest in a wide variety of other areas that could supply significant benefit to society. It is amazingly simple to think of education as an investment and to measure the returns produced by education, that is, the consumption of earlier investments, namely the consumption of each individual and society. This is an amazingly straightforward way of thinking about education. The role of marketing in the management and training of educational institutions is discussed (*ibid*). According to Jurkovic (1986), it is vital to use and deploy the limited material and human resources available to best serve the demands of training and education. In this framework, it finds two main motivations to question the functioning of economic efficiency standards as well as economic rules in social activities and thus in raising children and education.

6. Conclusion

Economic criteria are limited, as the primary tasks of social activities are often set outside the narrow sphere of economics. Since the primary social role of upbringing and education is to increase the amount of knowledge, this social function should never be questioned and should not be overshadowed by insisting on economic efficiency, which is the economic calculation of the resource's engagement with this function. Since the primary social role of training and education is to increase the amount of knowledge, this social function should never be questioned or

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overshadowed by the insistence on economic efficiency. He believes that the second element that hinders the application of economic principles to child rearing and education is the economic nature of these activities, as well as the wide variety of details that education itself offers as another activity. Since training and education investments are not simultaneous in terms of increasing the service supply and realizing the social benefits of these investments, it is not possible to apply economic laws related to the spontaneous functioning of the market mechanism and price flexibility. These laws include the laws of supply and demand, legal values, and legal substitution of more expensive inputs with cheaper ones. Moreover, it is impossible to apply economic laws associated with the spontaneous functioning of the market mechanism and price elasticity (ibid). Jac (1979) adds to these the many external economies created by training and education as public activities. These include enriching the life of an educated person, developing independence and creativity, contributing to science and education through the emergence of innovations, improving interpersonal relationships, more efficient and better management, etc. includes. Jac (1979) adds to these many external economies.

Another potential cause of erratic demand is insufficient activity to change participants' behavior and habits. Marketing efforts should make it possible to meet stable demand. Excessive demand occurs when an educational organization receives higher amounts of demand for its services than the organization can or can provide. Attractive schools and faculties regularly receive applications from more applicants interested in enrollment than they can objectively receive due to ability constraints by the training and educational institution. This is because ability constraints prevent the institution from receiving an excessive number of applications. In such cases, selective exclusion will apply, which will consider the advantages not only for students or learners, but also for the institution. Various classification methods are used to select the students who will benefit most from the given education program. The craving for dangerous substances that may be linked to deviant behavior such as drugs, alcohol and cigarettes has consequences for society, particularly in the younger half of the population. These effects are most felt by young people. One of the marketing tasks required in the field of education is the methodical action of changing people's routines and behaviors to reduce the demand for potentially dangerous products (ibid). This is conducted through actions aimed at educating participants to take an active role in society and for

changes, broadening their interests in various fields, and overcoming prejudices and false role models. Educational and training content that points to the harmfulness of some products and unacceptable behavior is also used. Training and education institutions help parents improve their parenting skills or access adequate health services through psychological counseling for parents and their children (Alfirevi , Relja , Popovi , 2016). Emphasis is placed on setting up parent-institutional cooperation in various teaching and extracurricular activities. Examining studies for parenting and education in an institution reveals the various challenges faced by the institution. Often, teachers will interpret the content, while students will listen, read, and keep it. Productive activities cannot be done because there are too many repetitive activities. Learning ready-made facts does happen, but the development of skills is rare. This is an important deficiency in one's academic performance (Meler, 1994: 172). There are both tangible (resources, people and money) and intangible (good reputation, long history, tradition, position on the lifecycle curve and adaptive potential) resources for training and educational institutions. The Role of Marketing in the Management of Training and Educational Institutions 285 (Meler, 1994). Whether a particular school or institution will adopt marketing as a way of solving these problems depends on the extent of the backlog of marketing difficulties, as well as management attitudes and their ability to use marketing in education. Marketing of parenting and educational institutions is a relatively new and useful field of study. In this field, students are increasingly recognized as consumers or users of services, emphasizing the commercial part of educational and training institutions. To be more specific, students have their own demands and expectations that must be met, which shows that an educational institution must accept the concept of the market (Gulbault , 2016).

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